

Time and Expansion of the Early Universe

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1 Introduction

The concept of time and space in physics has evolved significantly over the years, from classical ideas to relativity and quantum mechanics. Each framework adds a new layer to our understanding of the universe. Traditionally, time was seen as a constant, but Einstein revealed that time isn't absolute—it stretches and compresses, depending on factors like speed and gravity. Quantum mechanics further intertwines time and space, especially at the smallest scales, highlighting their distinct yet interconnected roles.

To truly understand time and space, we look back to the early universe, especially the moments right after the Big Bang. During this time, the universe expanded rapidly in a way that defies linear models, requiring nonlinear approaches to capture phenomena like inflation.

2 Methodology

This paper introduces a new approach that uses a matter-dominated scaling factor to calculate a more accurate size of the observable universe in its early stages. Instead of assuming a linear expansion, our equation accounts for the universe's dynamic history, showing the different stages of expansion that occurred. Using this scaling factor, we find that the universe expanded from 1 Planck Length to approximately 0.0026 billion light-years (or about 2,582 light-years) within the first three minutes, reflecting the nonlinear nature of early cosmic growth more accurately than linear estimates.

By comparing these nonlinear predictions with traditional models, we aim to provide a more precise tool for understanding the universe's initial moments. This equation isn't definitive but serves as an invitation for further refinement by other researchers.

3 Age Scaling Factor

To calculate the **size of the universe at 3 minutes after the Big Bang**, we consider:

1. **Expansion of the Universe:** The current expansion rate (67.4 km/s/Mpc) is far slower than the rate during the universe's high-energy early moments. However, assuming a constant expansion rate, we can estimate a "size" by scaling down the current radius based on the age ratio.
2. **Scaling with Time:** We simplify the estimation by scaling down the current size proportionally to the age ratio.

The Age Scaling Factor is calculated as:

$$AgeScalingFactor = \frac{Ageat3minutes}{CurrentAge}$$

Converting 3 minutes to years:

$$3minutes = \frac{3}{525600} \approx 5.707 \times 10^{-6} years$$

Using the current age of the universe, 13.787×10^9 years:

$$AgeScalingFactor = \frac{5.707 \times 10^{-6}}{13.787 \times 10^9} \approx 4.14 \times 10^{-16}$$

4 Estimated Size of the Universe at 3 Minutes

Applying this scaling factor to the current radius of the universe (46.5 billion light-years):

$$Radiusat3minutes = 4.14 \times 10^{-16} \times 46.5 \times 10^9 light - years \approx 0.019 light - years$$

Converting light-years to kilometers:

$$0.019 light - years \approx 1.8 \times 10^{12} km$$

Under a constant expansion assumption, the radius of the universe 3 minutes after the Big Bang would be approximately 1.8 trillion kilometers (or about 0.019 light-years).

5 Equation: Quantifying the Cosmos

I'll derive a general equation that takes inputs like the current age and radius of the universe, along with the age at a given time after the Big Bang. This will allow the results to be reproduced and adapted as needed.

5.1 Given Inputs and Equation Derivation

Inputs: Current Radius of the Observable Universe = $R_{current}$ (e.g., 46.5 billion light – years)
Current Age of the Universe = $T_{current}$ (e.g., 13.787 billion years)
Age at Desired Time After Big Bang = $T_{desired}$ (e.g., 3 minutes)

Equation for Age Scaling Factor:

$$AgeScalingFactor = \frac{T_{desired}}{T_{current}}$$

Equation for Radius at Desired Time: Using the scaling factor to estimate the universe's radius at $T_{desired}$,

$$R_{desired} = AgeScalingFactor \times R_{current}$$

or equivalently,

$$R_{desired} = \frac{T_{desired}}{T_{current}} \times R_{current}$$

6 Limitations and Refinements

The linear scaling model provides an approximation, not accounting for nonlinear expansion due to inflation. The more accurate equation for the universe's scale factor in a matter-dominated era is:

$$a(t) = \left(\frac{t}{T_{current}} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}}$$

Using this, the refined equation for the universe's radius at time $T_{desired}$ is:

$$R_{desired} = \left(\frac{T_{desired}}{T_{current}} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} \times R_{current}$$

7 Example Calculation with Refined Model

Given:

$$R_{current} = 46.5 \text{ billion light – years}$$

$$T_{current} = 13.787 \text{ billion years}$$

$$T_{desired} = 3 \text{ minutes} = 5.707 \times 10^{-6} \text{ years}$$

Substitute into the refined equation:

$$R_{desired} = \left(\frac{5.707 \times 10^{-6}}{13.787} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} \times 46.5 \text{ billion light – years}$$

8 Conclusion

This refined equation gives a more accurate approximation of the observable universe's radius shortly after the Big Bang, better reflecting early cosmic expansion conditions and laying a foundation for further refinement.